

HORIZON 2020

Research and Innovation action

Grant Agreement No. 730965

ARICE: Arctic Research Icebreaker Consortium:

**A strategy for meeting the needs for marine-based research
in the Arctic**

Deliverable 4.2. Online registration system set up

Submission of Deliverable

Work Package	WP4
Deliverable no. & title	D4.2. Online registration system set up
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Last change	
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Lead Beneficiary	AWI (partner 1)
Contributors	<input type="checkbox"/> 1 – AWI, <input type="checkbox"/> 2 – SPRS, <input type="checkbox"/> 3 - NPI, <input type="checkbox"/> 4 - ULAVAL, <input type="checkbox"/> 5 – UAF/CFOS, <input type="checkbox"/> 6 – AP, <input type="checkbox"/> 7 – CSIC-UTM, <input type="checkbox"/> 8 – CNR, <input type="checkbox"/> 9 - WOC, <input type="checkbox"/> 10 – IOPAN, <input type="checkbox"/> 11 – FMI, <input type="checkbox"/> 12 - CNRS, <input type="checkbox"/> 13 – NERC-BAS, <input type="checkbox"/> 14 – DTU-AQUA
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Deliverable No. 4.2.

Online registration system set up

Abstract

An online registration system has been set up with the **PT (outline** tool from **the DLR Project Management Agency**, to create an unique online submission point, management and review of proposals submitted to the ARICE Call for ship time.

Proposals to the **ARICE 2018 call for ship-time proposals** can be submitted through this link till the 5th of July at 15:00h CEST:

<https://secure.pt-dlr.de/ptoutline/app/arice2018>

The screenshot shows a web browser window with the URL <https://secure.pt-dlr.de/ptoutline/app/arice2018>. The page features the PT-Outline logo and navigation links for Site notice, Privacy, and Support. The main content area is titled "ARICE2018" and describes the "ARCTIC RESEARCH ICEBREAKER CONSORTIUM - Call ARICE2018". It provides information on the online submission of ship-time proposals for PRV Polarstern, CCGS Amundsen, and RV Sikuliaq, with a link to www.arice.eu for more details. Below this, there is a login section with tabs for "Login", "Sign up", and "Recover password". The login form includes fields for "E-Mail:" and "Password", a "Login" button, and a "Forgot your password?" link. The footer of the page includes the copyright notice "Copyright ©" and the DLR Projektträger logo.

Detailed submission guidelines are downloadable from the ARICE Website to facilitate the process, and have been included in D4.3.